

Ugly Face of Rape Among Female Dalits in Western Uttar Pradesh : A Sociological Study

Abstract

**"Violence against Women Costs
The community – socially and Economically
A society which is unsafe for women is unsafe for everyone"**

In any nation the cultural manners and the condition of society is analyzed and evaluated by the condition of women of that era and we can say that the developed civilization and cultures of society always analysis by their living status of women.

Keywords: Sociological Study, Violence against Women, Female Dalits.

Introduction

India's population as on 15th national serve 2011 stood at 1.210,193,422 (623, 724, 248 males and 586, 174 females). During this period i.e., 2001 to 2011 the peoples who belong to scheduled caste in India are increased by 35 millions. The censuses figures have shown that there are 201.4 Millions Hindu, Sikh, Budhhist dalits in India and the ratio of increment for Dalit peoples are about 20.8% that is much higher than the general population. The general population had increased only 17.7% of total population of India. That's mean the overall SC share of the population also have increased from 16.2% to 16.6%. India's demographic imbalance number for scheduled caste people of which there are 103.5 millions males and 97.9 millions females and they are alienated among the 29 states and 7 Union territories across the country and the highest population of Dalit peoples resides in state of Uttar Pradesh only, i.e. More than 40 million Dalits population in the entire region of Uttar Pradesh reside.

Who are Dalits?

The word "Dalit" comes from the Sanskrit root of dal- and means "Broken, ground-down, downtrodden or oppressed". Those previously known as untouchables, depressed classes, and Harijans are today increasingly adopting the terms "Dalit" as a name for themselves. In ancient India, the upper class of people have always neglected and prejudiced Dalits.

But Dalit women faced double discrimination on the basis of caste class and gender in all spheres of their life and subject to gross violation of their physical integrity, including sexual abuse by dominant castes. Police statistics data over the past 5 years shows that 3 dalit women are raped every day by dominant caste. Awareness among dalit women as 'inferior' and untouchable', as sexually available, as inherently criminal in nature, and as available for all forms of violence, especially sexual violence contribute to their specific vulnerability to violence National Human Right commission has stated that numbers of rape against scheduled caste women are increasing day by day and most of rape is used by 'upper' caste militias as a weapon to break morale of the entire communist. Rape is used as political instrument, and wrath of the dominant castes. Moreover, in some villages across India, dominate castes continue to perceive their 'right to rape of' dalit women even today. In India the conviction rate for rapes against Dalit women in under 2% compared to 9% conviction rate in total of 25% in rape cases against all women in India.

Some Common Terms that Involved in Violence against Women are

Incest, Sexual abuse, Rape, Date Rape, Sexual assault, where drugs or alcohol was used as weapon., Indecent behavior, Indecent assault, Sexual molesting Child Sexual abuse and child sexual assault but here this paper is focuses on terms Rape among female Dalits only.

In India only Dalits constitute about percent of India's population

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in 2011 with less than half being women which means that 80 million Dalit women face multiple forms of discrimination in this country alone.

According to 2013 statistics in every week, 21 Dalit women are being raped and 13 Dalits are murdered. The Crime against Dalits are increasing since 2000.

According to survey, in 2003, there were 1089 cases of Dalit women being raped by Dalit men while it increased to 1446 in 2006. The conviction rate in case of Dalit atrocity is just 5.3% in 2006.

For sociological study, the problem of rape against female Dalits is a burning issue. Therefore to undertake a study of this aspect in specific region or a specific area is justified.

Objectives of the Study

The two main objectives are proposed to study in the present work.

1. To know who are victimized women—On the basis of this objective the social background of the victims have been tried to analyze. The facts about the residential area, marital status, family status, age, education etc. of the victims have been tried to know.
2. To know who are the victimizers of rape against Dalit women—On the basis of this objective the relationship of victimizers with the victims have been analyzed.

Brief Overview of Selected Literature on Rape against Dalit Women in India.

Rape is one of the most heinous forms of violence against women. It may be reiterated that official data on violence against women have been reported to suffer several limitations. This is more true to sex offences against women in general, and rape in particular as most rape cases go unreported because the victims are so upset and ashamed to report it, the social stigma attached to rape is deterrent enough to reporting such cases. She is afraid of the reaction of those closer to her, whether husband, parents, relative or friend. In the case of young victims, the parents wish to protect the child from the publicity of the legal ordeal. If the rapist is a father, brother, brother-in-law, brother's close friend or close relative, there are additional pressures not to report. It may be mentioned that rape is the only crime where harassment, guilt, shame, humiliation and social disapproval are attached to the victims, not to the offender (K.P. Krishna, 1993: 58)

In Indian society, rape victimization is not unique to the particular age or caste group. Some of the cases reported in the newspapers have involved victims below five years of age. In a systematic study (Bajaj, Joshi and Krishna, 1983), it has been observed that the proportion of victims of rape is the highest in the age group of 7-16 years. Further, it has been observed that a large number of unmarried women are victimized as compared to married and widowed (K.P. Krishna, 1993: 58)

Ram Ahuja (1987) found that it is not only the poor girls who become rape victims but even the employees belonging to the middle class are sexually humiliated by their employers. Women inmates in jails

are raped by the superintendents, women crime suspects by police officers, women patients by hospital personnel, maid servants by their masters and women daily wage earners by contractors and middlemen. Even deaf and dumb, lunatic and blind, and women beggars are not spared. The victims face social stigma and disgrace and suffer serious guilt-pangs and personality disorders if they register protests. (quoted by Ram Ahuja, 1992:215)

Ram Ahuja in his empirical study on "Violence against women" (1987), found that rape does not always occur between total strangers, maximum cases of rapes are situational (Quoted by Ram Ahuja, 1992 : 214-218)

About sexual violence, Deep Punia (1985) mentioned that most of the rape victims were unmarried at the time of crime. It has been also found that most of the victims were dependents, unemployed or students. The rapist and victims in most of the cases were from the middle class and lower socio-economic strata.

Area of Study and Methodology

A survey was conducted in the district of Meerut, Ghaziabad and Gautam Budha Nagar (Noida) of western Uttar Pradesh for the purpose of study and data also collected from various Hindi and English News papers namely Amar Ujala, Dainik Jagran, Hindustan Time, I-next and the columns of these news papers were also regarding "Rape among female Dalits in Meerut, Ghaziabad, & Gautam Budh Nagar (Noida) districts during the period of one year from March 2014 to March 2015 have been collected. The news items were categorized accordingly. Besides collecting the data from primary sources also. For this purpose 30 rape victims were interviewed with the help of others and some shocking facts came to our concern so therefore some important findings are here below;

Findings

1. Mostly rape victims are often employed in agricultural farms owned by higher caste feudal landlords. During the course of their work in the field they are often sexually exploited by their feudal lords.
2. Majority of the victims belong to 18-30 years of age group and are mostly school and college going girls.
3. It has also been found that victims of rural area were married while victims of urban area are remain mostly unmarried.
4. Most of the rape victims were unmarried at the time of crime.
5. The rapist and victims in most of the cases were from the middle class and lower socio-economic stratum.
6. The rapist in majority of cases known victims, mainly they are close relative friends or neighbor.
7. As the victim faces social stigma, disgrace and suffer serious guilt-pain, therefore about 52% of the rape cases were not reported to the police station because the parents of the young and minor girl victims are wish to protect their girl child from the stigma in large of protect from the legal orders. If the rapist is a father, brother of a

closed relative they put pressure over the victim for not to report this incident.

8. It has been found that not only the poor girls but even the employees, belonging to the middle class are also sexually humiliated by their employers.
9. Most of the culprits belong to upper caste and are of high socio-economic status.
10. It has also been found that sexual abuse has been reported as an important cause of suicide.
11. In most cases, the rape victims have been murdered by their relatives the violation of a woman's chastity is viewed as an affront to the families honors.

Suggestions

Perhaps this is not quandary of Dalit women that they can get protection from low enforcement nor any one can help from other caste or class of the society. Further they are not aware of rights and they are constantly abused by other sections of society. In order to help dalit women there are many steps which have to be taken in order to protect them such as.

1. Mass campaign programme which will spread knowledge about rights and freedoms of Dalit women: Apart from government Mass campaign to promote the efforts of government to remove cast abused violence.
2. Effective implementation of government policies made specifically for the protection of Dalits women;
3. Availability of Psycho-socio counselor in Dalit settlement cases : as caste base of violence and crime against Dalit women are very sensitive in nature if is necessary to employ psyco-socio counselor for dealing with such issue.
4. Limited use or prohibition on alcoholic drinks as they work as catalyst in ceasing violence. More strict rules should be made for consumption and use of alcoholic drinks are they tend to make people more aggressive and violent.
5. Witness protection programme : In many cases, witnesses are murdered in order to drop cases against other class of people in such cases it is necessary to introduce witness protection programme.
6. Government should ensure rehabilitation of the victims or survivors of the crime. Rehabilitation of victims of crimes is very important as the psychological effects of crimes on Dalit women are very dangerous and therefore government should enforce rehabilitation of victims of Crime.

Conclusion

The situation of Dalit women in India is getting worse day by day and needs immediate attention of Government to formulate and implement new policy to protect them. Dalit females need to be empowered through education, employment opportunities, legal literacy and human rights education. Government, Police makers, community groups, the civil society and non-government organizations need to formulate an effective strategy to stop this inhuman activity last but not least dalit women have to themselves wake up and rise to fight for their rights and dignity as god helps those who

help themselves. In this regard some one has rightly said.

“लगा कर आग घूंघट में, उठे जो देश की नारी
इन्ही हवस के पुजारियों पर, पड जाए एक दिन भारी,
इन्ही गहनो, इन्ही जेवरों ने इन्हे बनाया है बन्दी,
उतार फेंक इन बेडियों को आज हर नारी।”

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